

Deliverable D3.8 - Feedback on the recommendation of infrastructure solutions for distributed analysis and federated learning

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Feedback on the recommendation of infrastructure solutions for distributed analysis and federated learning

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1. Executive Summary

Within GDI Pillar II is tasked with deploying the national nodes and ensuring these become operational, while Pillar III is tasked with bringing use case requirements and innovative solutions to Pillar II for deployment. One of the identified requirements from Pillar III is federated analysis, on which deliverable “D8.8 - Evaluation of distributed analysis and federated learning infrastructure solutions and recommendations for adoption” already identified and demonstrated a range of technical solutions to support federated analysis. This deliverable uses D8.8 as a basis, and reports on the work that has been done since then, both in Pillar II and with Pillar III to try and support the requirements for federated analysis within GDI.

With a wide range of different deployments across different national nodes, and different national priority use cases, it is important that any solution should support as many use cases as possible by using standards, helping ensure the data are as FAIR as possible in a federated context, as well as ensuring the sustainability of the infrastructure. Standards that have been adopted are described, as well as the work that has been performed to select these standards, especially the utilisation of User Journeys to try and ensure each deployed service or functionality supports as many use cases as possible. Additionally the work at node level to support federated computation in SPEs is described, and the status of this deployment as part of the work towards D3.6: ‘Video demonstrator showing data access based on a Pillar III use case.’

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers (e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 5</p>	No

Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.	
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	No

3. Methods

One of the aims of GDI is to support the distributed and federated analysis of genomic and associated phenotypic data hosted across different GDI nodes. Within GDI, Pillar II is responsible for the deployment of operational national nodes, primarily through work packages WP3 & 4, while Pillar III comprises two work packages, WP7 which interacts with the GDI use cases, and WP8 which proposes innovative solutions. Both these work packages generate ideas and proposals for new or extended functionalities or services to be deployed and supported by Pillar II across the national nodes.

As part of the initial process of understanding the possibilities for supporting distributed and federated computation, Pillar III submitted deliverable D8.8 - Evaluation of distributed analysis and federated learning Infrastructure solutions and recommendations for adoption¹ in March 2024 which demonstrated three examples of federated or distributed analysis based on different GDI use cases from WP7. The results of this deliverable, plus feedback on the existing GDI Starter Kit products from the different nodes, as well as outcomes from B1MG were analysed to identify synergies and unmet gaps between the expectations of both Pillars.

As part of the process of refining the possibilities for distributed and federated computation within GDI, Pillar II also attended the Pillar III workshop² held in Barcelona between 22 - 24 January 2024, where the expectations and responsibilities between Pillars II and III were discussed, including the federated and distributed analysis demonstrators being developed by Pillar III, and detailed in D8.8.

Pillar II then reviewed with then nodes their expected capabilities and expectations regarding federated or distributed analysis, and the options on how to support this, but asking the nodes to participate in to workshops, one held in Malta³ in March 2024, and the other in Brno⁴ in September 2024, which included a workshop on Federated Computation⁵.

Pillar II developed the GDI Starter Kit⁶, which initially included a 'Federated Computation' and a 'Containerised Computation' products, which would support the distributed and/or federated analysis at a node level. In conjunction with Pillar III, these products were merged to form a single 'Computation' product, with co-leadership from Pillars II and III (WP4 and WP8).

The Starter Kit in Pillar II was developed and deployed in two Milestones, MS7⁷ and MS8⁸, which demonstrated different access models including distributed computation in MS8. As part of MS8,

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10887365>

² https://docs.google.com/document/d/1OleoYa83HBEqUwKf25gavWoskx8FL-4t8i_VqP7prtE/edit?tab=t.o

³ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1iil_A5J7VGOen3RgSj2NuxPxYrvWocbP6ZV8ZE-ciU7Q/edit

⁴ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1QoUkxZDyuBy3m0yA22X-ygUR3nSSFy7ZttCzFGhf8lw/edit>

⁵ <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1jb3Mf55HCgSze33cHoEQwJ6OkFNQnlZs1leX1Fthu28/edit>

⁶ <https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/starter-kit>

⁷ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1RanvwS_AUvuBRFFOBilgx1EFnJO3VqWlB2Yln-5tPk8/edit

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14989034>

meetings were held with the nodes aiming to deploy the Starter kit to determine exactly what they could technically deploy and demonstrate as part of MS8/D3.6.

4. Description of work accomplished

The work comprised a review of the recommendations from Pillar III for federated analysis, understanding the node requirements and expectations, refining the decision making process and transfer of ideas between Pillars II & III, the deployments at a node level as part of the milestones and their support for 'federated analytics, and the creation of a user story to demonstrate federated analytics across the GDI.

4.1 Review of the demonstrators in D8.8

D8.8 described three demonstrators for distributed or federated analysis. These included

1. Polygenic risk score (PRS) for infectious disease,
2. Cancer data mobilisation
3. 5 safes RO-Crate compatible Trusted Research Environment

For the polygenic risk score (PRS), a Galaxy⁹ workflow was executed on three national Galaxy instances hosted in three separate countries, which ensured the raw genetic and phenotypic data remained in the local node. The returned results could include aggregated results determining the phenotype and PRS.

For the Cancer data mobilisation, the raw FASTQ files were analysed by a Galaxy instance hosted in Germany, which generated the vcf files with the called variants and associated minor allele frequencies (MAF), and uploaded the MAF files to Spain where these were loaded into cBioPortal¹⁰ with the structured clinical data already hosted at BSC.

The 5-safes¹¹ Research Object Crate¹² (RO-Crate) demonstrator ran a workflow written in Common Workflow Language¹³ (CWL) or Nextflow¹⁴ (or another workflow language) in a secure environment subject to appropriate approval from WfEXs¹⁵ in a Trusted Research Environment (TRE).

The main technologies used in the three demonstrators detailed in D8.8 are Galaxy, Nextflow, WfExS, cBioPortal and docker¹⁶ (or Podman¹⁷) containers. Pillar II reviewed these technologies and identified the commonalities, where they exist, between these technologies. The GA4GH Task Execution

⁹ <https://galaxyproject.org/>

¹⁰ <https://www.cbioportal.org/>

¹¹ <https://www2.uwe.ac.uk/faculties/BBS/Documents/1601.pdf>

¹² <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

¹³ <https://www.commonwl.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.nextflow.io/>

¹⁵ <https://wfexs-backend.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

¹⁶ <https://www.docker.com/>

¹⁷ <https://podman.io/>

Service^{18,19} (TES) is compatible with both Nextflow²⁰ (version 24.04), Galaxy²¹ (via Pulsar²²), and WfExS, so that a node which deploys the starter kit with TES should also be able to support the equivalent demonstrations to those performed by Pillar III without having to deploy additional services or infrastructure. Pillar II proposes support for Open Container Initiative²³ at node level, so that compatible container technologies, such as Docker, can be used without vendor lock at a node level. Additionally other projects and service providers, such as EOSC-ENTRUST²⁴, Microsoft Azure²⁵, & EuroScienceGateway^{26,27} have TES implementations.

4.2 Node deployments and expectations

As part of the interaction with the nodes, during the Malta workshop, as well as planning for milestones 7 & 8, Pillar II tried to understand the nodes' perspective on what can be possible within their national deployments. These informed the requirements that Pillar II tries to meet for the deployment within GDI:

- Where possible all processes use existing (global) standards, and where these standards do not enable the required functionality, the gaps are identified and brought to the standards setting organisation (e.g. GA4GH to leveraging GDI's position as a driver project)
 - This helps to ensure that a diverse range of use cases can be supported using the same technology - examples here which are globally used across many domains include TCP/IP, Open container standard, OIDC, OAuth 2.
 - Specific to bioinformatics / genomics include WorkflowHub, BioContainers, Dockstore, GA4GH standards, etc. Where possible, these specialisations should build on the standards above.
 - Use case specific software / technology stacks. These are the least sustainable to maintain within GDI, and as such Pillar II recommends that Pillar II supports the deployment of these tools, but not the specific tool itself. It would be for the node to specifically add support to one or more of these tools based on their specific use case(s). An analogy here would be to see GDI nodes as distributed cloud instances, e.g. IaaS, but not the tools specific support unless this is specifically funded.
- Scope of Pillar II responsibilities must be limited to that which ensures GDI as a federated infrastructure works. The GDI funding mechanism allows for the nodes themselves to adapt

¹⁸ <https://ga4gh.github.io/task-execution-schemas/docs/>

¹⁹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2405.00013>

²⁰ <https://seqera.io/blog/nextflow-24.04-highlights/>

²¹ <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae410>

²² <https://galaxyproject.org/ga4gh/>

²³ <https://opencontainers.org/>

²⁴ <https://eosc-entrust.eu/>

²⁵ <https://github.com/microsoft/ga4gh-tes>

²⁶ <https://eosc.eu/eu-project/eurosciencegateway/>

²⁷ <https://galaxyproject.org/projects/esg/>

their own deployments, adding functionalities, concentrating on specific use cases as they see fit via their national funding contribution to GDI.

- Pillar II is constrained in what it can do across all nodes by the nodes own priorities and capabilities. The nodes are very diverse, with a diverse range of expectations, priority use cases, and existing infrastructures they wish to engage with.

4.3 Pillar II & III Collaborations

Given the existing work that has been done in Pillar III, as well as the deployment milestones in Pillar II, Pillar II & III collaborated to identified a methodology to ensure alignment between the Pillars for bringing novel and innovative solutions identified by Pillar III into Pillar II, while ensuring that they were deployable and sustainable. This decision process (Figure 1) includes the support for the development of distributed and federated computation at a node level, prior to the formal RFC process coming into operation²⁸

Given the close alignment of the Pillars to support the federated computation use case, regular meetings to work on support for federated computation within the GDI, which include representatives from both Pillars II & III, producing a user story to showcase GDI's capabilities and value via the support for federated computation²⁹

A set of User Journeys³⁰ were developed by Pillar III outlining a research user's journey from discovering data of interest, to accessing and performing an analysis of these data, based on the requirements of the use cases detailed in deliverable D7.5 - 'Report to identify the initial set of recommendations for addressing use cases.'³¹ These User Journeys helped with the development of the services deployed by the nodes, and the determination of which services should be deployed in production, and those which could be demonstrated.

As GDI has four distinct and separate use cases in WP7, the infrastructure deployed at a node level should be as agnostic to the specific use case as possible - i.e. the core infrastructure should support any specific specialisations, such as platforms or software, required by the different use cases on a generic infrastructure. While the original Starter Kit included products aimed at software containerization and basic federated computation as described in the Beyond 1 Million Genomes (B1MG) deliverable 'D4.3 - Secure cross-border data access roadmap'³² — mainly focused on deploying OCI containers and providing a GA4GH TES endpoint for triggering local executions — the incorporation of Pillar III's feedback helped support the WP7 use cases.

²⁸<https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/rfcs>

²⁹ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1wizr8-NCmohnYeJBo9mzGB-6KxelbfhNGdX_RTSl1U/edit?tab=t.0#heading=h.cungr8gotyiv

³⁰ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1QDeRvtWWrhMj2Brzpetx9wzupQfo-Rx8Xd53Qi9TWS/edit?>

³¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14537082>

³² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10046981>

A simple illustration of the decision path for incorporating new features in the reference implementation. (Later, this will be replaced by SOP:s etc.)

Legend

Description of the illustration

- Time runs from left to right.
- The next step occurs only when there is an agreement to continue at the previous step.
- Each step can include discussions and improvements.
- The upper part of the illustration is common, while the lower interactions with dashed arrows occur when applicable.
- The final decision to create a reference implementation is displayed as an handshake in the illustration.
- A rejected idea may be reiterated in pillar III and suggested later as an improved idea.

Figure 1: Depiction of the decision process utilised by the different GDI Pillars in understanding the novel solutions proposed by Pillar III.

To try and align the requirements of different projects for federated computation, representatives of GDI Pillars II & III attended the ELIXIR AHM meeting workshop on 'Deciphering federated analysis: What is it and how far can it take us'³³, as well as the workshop on 'Identifying challenges to interoperability and gaps in GA4GH Standards'³⁴, which included a specific section on GDI implementation of GA4GH standards, including TES, which is a core part of the GDSI Starter Kit at node level.

³³ https://docs.google.com/document/d/13aCXWW8gnv9AYvPUDyOLO_oBQYacsW3EpJ9lKk5OzbM/edit

³⁴ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1lx-aaucYUAUH3dCrU1JeGcJofZBttuPak9Moo0EQ7DF/edit>

4.4 Deployment Milestones

Pillar II had a set of deployment milestones during 2024, the last of which was milestone 8, detailed and described in deliverable 3.6. This milestone demonstrated a core set of user journeys, from ujGdio1 to ujGdio7, with a stretch goal of ujGdio8 and ujGdio9 at a node level which detailed the executing and return of results of an analysis run on an SPE. Specifically for the stretch goal, two nodes deployed a TES endpoint which could accept tasks and execute these tasks within a SPE hosted at the node, and return the results to a secure location for the user to download.

4.5 Federated Computation Demonstration User Story

Based on D8.8, D7.7, and milestones MS7 and MS8, and to facilitate the development of the GDI requirements for federated computation, "usGdi13 - identify repetitive sequences in large population groups" has been developed by the Federated Computation Task Force and was presented³⁵ at the General Assembly in November 2024 by Pillar III. The task at hand, taken from the cancer use case (WP7), is to analyse repetitive sequences in genomic datasets across national nodes using custom workflows and tools, and includes the following steps:

- Dataset Discovery
- Tool Selection or Submission
- Workflow Creation or Selection
- Workflow Execution
- Result Retrieval

To support this the following features must be supported:

- Federated Dataset Processing
- Customisable Analytical Workflows
- Efficient Data Management
- Collaborative Research

This user story is supported by the architecture indicated in Figure 3, which is an updated version of the architecture presented by Pillar III at the General Assembly in 2024. The main updates to the diagram versus the one presented³⁶ at the General Assembly are:

- A. The linking of the 'Computation Passport' to the LS AAI
- B. The undefined component that links the 'Storage and Interfaces' to the 'Containerised Computation'.

³⁵
https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1jWbE3ix4VWVeUb13zDdWeZn5TnVY2oI7HY8OPoMbw/edit?slide=id.g3150cafo1b1_2_162#slide=id.g3150cafo1b1_2_162

³⁶
https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1jWbE3ix4VWVeUb13zDdWeZn5TnVY2oI7HY8OPoMbw/edit?slide=id.g3150cafo1b1_2_176#slide=id.g3150cafo1b1_2_176

For (A), at least within the timescale of GDI, the authorisation to access a particular compute resource can be performed by the user's identity within the institution providing the service, which can be linked to the LS AAI identity via the LinkedIdentities³⁷ visa. This has been demonstrated in Milestone 7³⁸, where a user was able to log in and access both compute and data at CSC based on their LS AAI identity. The prerequisite for this are that a) the user has an LS AAI identity, b) the user also has a CSC identity, and c) the user has linked these identities via the LinkedIdentities visa. In the CSC use case, the appropriate recording of resource usages, such as storage or compute, are recorded via the CSC identity and billed to the appropriate cost centre, therefore within GDI an appropriate funding mechanism would need to be defined and managed to ensure that costs for each institution providing computation services are accounted for correctly.

For (b), at CSC for the GDI use case this service is provided for via the 'REMS Central' and a FUSE layer component which enables access to the data indicated in the ControlledAccessVisa issued by the 'REMS Central'. The FUSE layer also decrypts the data as it is accessed, so a container may perform some form of analysis on these data. However, the implementation of this component is diverse between nodes, primarily because of the key handling required to decrypt the data which is encrypted at rest in 'Storage and Interfaces'. The data in the 'Storage and Interfaces' is encrypted, and if it uses the recommended Crypt4GH the encryption of the header is done via asymmetric keys, so to decrypt the data a user specific public key is required. A standardised way to manage the public key in a federated context, using standards such as using TES or WES, is being worked on by GA4GH. The '?' for the 'REMS' component at a node is due to the open question of whether a node will maintain its own set of controlled access grants, or rely on the 'REMS Central' for these. From now on we will call this missing component 'Local REMS'.

³⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xgen.2021.100030>

³⁸ <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1-8gAesRHTZ4aYlkchJV7BRRSeEYPKCWb/edit>

Figure 3: Updated version of the Pillar III Federated Computation architecture diagram presented at the General Assembly in November 2024 based on the exercise done by Federated Computation Task Force to understand the product landscape and identify technical gaps that should be filled, as well as lessons learnt from both Milestones 7 & 8.

5. Results

- Maximising interoperability and applicability across use cases by use of GA4GH TES standard, including support for Galaxy and Nextflow as described in D8.8
- Improved communication between Pillar II & III
- Proof-of-concept node deployments of TES endpoints on an SPE

The support of TES (and WES if required) within the GDI infrastructure should allow the deployed nodes to support the different analytical use cases and demonstrations without requiring additional services to support federated computation. This is achieved through the portability and efficient deployment of containers, along with meeting the specific requirements of each use case. TES also allows different orchestrators or workflow managers to be utilised to execute tasks across the federated infrastructure depending on the use case, for example Galaxy or Nextflow, and hence reduces the possibility of vendor lock-in and increases the adaptability of the infrastructure to new technological developments.

The alignment of Pillars II & III on the requirements and support for federated analytics within GDI have become clearer through this work, especially the communication channels, such as the

decision process, and the regular meetings on federated analytics. The monthly cross-pillar meetings across GDI have helped manage expectations and clarify the scope of what can realistically be achieved in terms of federated computation. They have also ensured that the federated analytics demonstration is clearly defined and planned before the end of the GDI project.

After the deployment at the two candidate nodes of a TES endpoint on top of an SPE, there is a greater understanding within Pillar II of how distributed and federated analysis can be performed at a node level within an SPE and how this could be built in future, and these lessons will be brought to other nodes aiming to deploy nodes capable of distributed and federated analysis. The same processes can be extended to support the GA4GH Workflow Execution Service³⁹ (WES) as well, should this be necessary to fully support the requirements of federated computation, the Pillar III WP7 Use Cases, and the 1+MG ambition.

6. Discussion

- A demonstrator has been deployed that can allow analysis without giving the user access to the raw data, improving data security and reducing the risk of a data breach
- The need for a suitable repository of containers and workflows has been identified, as well as a process for approving the execution of these workflows and containers on GDI infrastructure and data
- Use of standards allows different deployments between nodes to be accommodated

The Pillar II demonstrator (3) (outlined in [section 4.1](#)) showcasing a remote analysis on a node returning aggregated and non-personal results to the user is an example of a federated analysis - federation of a single node - that could be possibly performed with a lower level of assurance (LoA) when the user is granted full access to the personal data contained within a dataset. Conceptually, this analysis is similar to a Beacon query where a user performs an analysis to determine the number of different individuals within a dataset with a certain set of characteristics (for example the number of males within dataset X with a mutation in the TLR7 gene). The only difference lies in the type of analysis performed. If the analysis has been pre-approved and does not expose personal data, then the required LoA for the infrastructure could be lower, since a higher LoA does not reduce the risk or impact of a data breach in this case.

In milestone 8, and described in D3.6, two nodes successfully deployed a TES endpoint that was accessible from outside the hosting institution and could execute a TES compatible workflow on the institution's provided SPE. To execute a task on these endpoints a user had to log in via LS AAI. The stretch goal was to help the institutions determine the infrastructure required to support distributed and federated analytics, including communication protocols, as well as the adherence to institutional and national data protection legislation, including GDPR.

³⁹ <https://github.com/ga4gh/workflow-execution-service-schemas>

At CSC the deployment was not limited to the source of the containers that could be executed, but limiting the source of containers for executed containers to pre-approved repositories, e.g. a Tools marketplace, is a configuration issue, and the endpoint can be configured as such once such a repository or marketplace has been defined. However, further work is needed in this area. If we assume that all analytical software in GDI will be properly containerized, then the project will require a system to manage which containers — i.e., analytical tools — can be run on each dataset. This is essential to ensure that the granularity of the results complies with the data-sharing agreements set by dataset owners, including local and national data protection regulations.

The TES endpoint deployed at the two nodes was a different implementation, for Sweden the TES endpoint was the version⁴⁰ used in the Starter Kit (which is based on Funnel⁴¹), while in Finland the TES endpoint was a deployment of TESK⁴². This indicates how the use of standards allows for, and supports, the diversity of deployments between different GDI nodes while providing the same functionality. Issues with differences in interpretation of the standard can be brought back to GA4GH where discovered via the proposed monitoring described in 'D5.5 - Report outlining QoS metrics, reporting processes, and Node TRLs defined'⁴³. This supports one of the Pillar II requirements to allow nodes to adapt the deployed infrastructure to their own requirements and priority use cases.

7. Conclusions & Impact

- Different use cases supported by the same node level deployment and compatible with work being done with EOSC-ENTRUST and EuroScienceGateway

The use of standards and specifications within the GDI, and especially for the federated and distributed computation, is ensuring that the GDI can support the different use cases which are supported by the user journeys. At a node level, these standards and specifications allow a diverse range of infrastructure to support not only different use cases, but different projects and even data types while maintaining interoperability, and conform to the work being done in EOSC-ENTRUST and EuroScienceGateway.

8. Next steps

- Define and deploy the Tools and Workflows marketplaces, The Computation dashboard, the Data Deposition dashboard, and Workflow Manager, and ensure the sustainability of these services, as well as the deployment location and integration (if any) with the User Portal
- Determine the processes needed to approve the workflows and containers for operation on GDI infrastructure and accessing GDI hosted data

⁴⁰ <https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/starter-kit-containerized-computation>

⁴¹ <https://ohsu-comp-bio.github.io/funnel/>

⁴² <https://github.com/elixir-cloud-aai/TESK/tree/master>

⁴³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10256901>

- Investigate the possibility of extending the cancer mobilisation use case to other use cases, including data preparation, quality control, and loading.

The Starter Kit can be extended to include WES if required, and determination of specific requirements for this should be performed. As shown in Figure 3, the Tools and Workflow marketplaces, the Computation as well as Data Deposition Dashboards, and the Workflow Manager need to be determined and their location and sustainability agreed. Nodes need to clarify if they will accept and trust ControlledAccessGrants visa issued centrally, or only at a node level, so the requirement for a 'Local REMS' (which maintains the ControlledAccessGrants visa at the node) can be finalised across the GDI infrastructure.

Working with Pillars I & III, limitations need to be defined on which containers (e.g. analytical software) can be run, where they can be run and under what conditions. Open questions include will the marketplace handle the container repository or should this be moved at node level? Additionally the specific type of central workflow orchestrator, should one be provided by GDI, needs to be planned, and its location determined for deployment. A location suitable for the upload of the final results for any analysis must also be determined, and whether this location is another trusted SPE for operation on aggregated results (e.g. of the user), or a specific location for access by the user. All of these could be co-located with the User Portal, providing the user with a single interface to discover, apply for, submit analyses on, and receive the analytics results from datasets hosted within the GDI.

In conjunction with 1+MG WG9, and detailed in B1MG deliverable "D4.3 - Secure cross-border data access roadmap"⁴⁴ there are proposals to utilise the existing infrastructure to extend the Pillar III demonstrator (2), cancer mobilisation. For example at CSC, the analytical pipeline needed to call the variants, annotation them, and prioritise them has already been containerised and run via SD Desktop. This could be moved to the SPE, ePouta, allowing a user to generate a list of variants without having access to the raw data. This workflow could easily be extended to support the generation of the MAF for the called variants, and to format these, along with associated phenotypic information, into a format suitable for load into cBioPortal. The user could then log into SD Desktop and spin up a VM containing cBioPortal, which can access and load the data generated by the previous variant calling pipeline.

The same process that has been outlined above can be generalised and hence extended to other use cases, with their own specific platforms, such as the RD-Connect Genome Phenome Analysis Platform⁴⁵ (GPAP) for rare disease, or analysing the results of a GWAS analysis for infectious disease. Such a system would help overcome current trust issues with providing access to the raw genomic and phenotypic data.

Ideally, the proposed GDI federated analysis service should align with the FAIR principles for computational workflows⁴⁶ by supporting provenance tracking. This means capturing the history of

⁴⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10046981>

⁴⁵ <https://rd-connect.eu/what-we-do/omics/gpap/>

⁴⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-04451-9>

dataset derivation, including the computational steps and other datasets involved, and hence supporting the management of the data within GDI. Provenance is a core component of the FAIR principles, particularly in promoting data reusability. Workflows should therefore record the provenance of each run. To ensure interoperability, provenance data must be represented in a formal, accessible, shared, and transparent format, with clear references to related objects and workflow components. For greater reusability, provenance records should document both the workflow and its resulting outputs. To support standardized provenance exchange, the community has developed frameworks such as W3C PROV⁴⁷ and the Workflow Run RO-Crate⁴⁸. These provide structured formats for packaging provenance information alongside related artifacts like workflow specifications and input/output data. By offering machine-actionable representations of workflows and their executions, the GDI federated analysis service would improve interoperability and enable broader reuse.

⁴⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-overview/>

⁴⁸ <https://www.researchobject.org/workflow-run-crate/>

